

Research Internship Opportunity

Initial application of cheminformatics methods
for bioinorganic catalyst design

Topic

While artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have been successfully applied to organic molecules for drug discovery, there remain significant opportunities in their application to (bio)inorganic molecules for catalyst predictive modeling and design in the circular economy.

Students interested in gaining practical experience in the computational side of inorganic chemistry are invited to apply for a research internship which will cover four aspects:

Review > ChemPlusChem, 2020, May;6(5):1044–1052. doi: 10.1002/cplu.202000252.
Robust Guanidine Metal Catalysts for the Ring-Opening Polymerization of Lactide under Industrially Relevant Conditions

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Affiliations + expand
PMID: 32449840 DOI: 10.1002/cplu.202000252


```
for molfile_path in tqdm(sorted(HERE.glob("*.mol")), leave=False):  
    pubmed_id, _sep, catalyst_name = molfile_path.stem.partition("_")  
  
    molecule = Chem.MolFromMolFile(molfile_path.as_posix(), sanitize=sanitize)  
    if molecule is None:  
        tqdm.write(f"error on {molfile_path}")  
        continue  
  
    if molecule.GetNumConformers() == 0:  
        raise ValueError(f"no coordinates found in {molfile_path.name}")  
    molecules.append(molecule)
```


1. The **curation** of a database of chemical structures, properties, and reactions

2. **Programming** in Python and using the RDKit cheminformatics package

3. The **visualization** and **exploration** of catalyst chemical space and trends in the recent literature

4. The **training** and **evaluation** of machine learning models, e.g., quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR)

Supervision and Application

This research internship will be supervised by Charles Tapley Hoyt within the Herres-Pawlis group. Prior knowledge in programming is preferred, but not required for students who demonstrate high aptitude.

Please send applications to Prof. Sonja Herres-Pawlis (sonja.herres-pawlis@ac.rwth-aachen.de) with charles.hoyt@ac.rwth-aachen.de CC'd.

